

An Intelligent Knowledge Management for Machining System

Ghelase Daniela¹, Daschievici Luiza²

Department of SIM, Dunarea de Jos University, Galati, Romania

Abstract— Today, information has become more important. Even data, information and knowledge are often used as if they have same meaning. This problem raises difficulties in engineering. It is necessary to exist a knowledge management system to avoid increased costs, waste of time and increased errors. Knowledge management is a comprehensive process of knowledge creation, knowledge validation, knowledge presentation, knowledge distribution and knowledge application. In this paper, knowledge management has been explained in general. Then as an example for this study, machining system has been considered, and an application of Knowledge Management in engineering has been attempted to explain. The paper proposes a knowledge management to achieve a competitive control of the machining systems. The model can be used by the manager for the choosing of competitive orders.

Keywords— *Competitive control, Information technology, Knowledge management, Machining system, Marketing knowledge.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A general definition has been ‘getting the right information to the right people at the right time’ in order for them to make better decisions.

Due to technology facilitates the rapid exchange of information, the pace of acquisition is growing exponentially in both large and small enterprises. The vast amounts of knowledge possessed by the enterprises are spread across countless structured and unstructured sources.

To improve processes and bring new products to the market faster and more cheaply, the enterprises have to identify, make available and apply this knowledge.

It is necessary to exist a knowledge management system and coordination between disciplines to avoid increased costs, waste of time and increased errors. Thus, information must be understood, organized and transformed for problems solving.

Consequently, information transformed in product is knowledge and coordination of this kind of knowledge is made by means of knowledge management.

The manufacturing industry faces the challenge of responding quickly to the ever-changing requirements of customers. It is necessary that in these high competitive environments, enterprises to control production system dynamics of such as:

- change in the product types and variants;
- change in the production quantities.

Enterprises have to develop and implement more responsive and flexible manufacturing systems based on knowledge. By this way, they can respond to outgoing and difficult to predict change in production requirements and make products with high quality, low cost and fast delivery.

The market dynamics is further passed to the mode of operation and management. In a knowledge-based society and economy, operations such as determining the relevant information and aggregating them into pieces of knowledge must be automated, because in such a complex and unpredictable environment, they are indispensable tools for creating, searching and structuring knowledge. The interaction between the economic environment and the manufacturing system is a major source of knowledge about the economic environment and the manufacturing system themselves [3].

II. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN ENGINEERING

Information is becoming ever more important in engineering. It is not suitable to use data, information and knowledge conventionally. That is there is conceptual confusion. Also, today's technological products need interaction between different disciplines. So the confusion increases more. At the multidisciplinary engineering system, any discipline contains some information peculiar to system. However, most of the information mean essentially same even if they are expressed in

different terms in different disciplines. Therefore, the available information must be evaluated, simplified and transformed into usable form that is knowledge.

Next, the knowledge is coordinated and connected with the system. So, a kind of know-how is acquired for the technological product. This case is generally based on a model, while it has special characteristics. An example of machining system has been analyzed in the following section. The model produced by technical knowledge which is acquired by the interaction of data, information and knowledge, by the coordination and the application of them on engineering system. KM model is presented in Fig. 1.

KM is a comprehensive process of knowledge creation, knowledge validation, knowledge presentation, knowledge distribution and knowledge application [2]. When KM model is applied by the enterprise into its production process it is obtained increasing competitiveness of the product in the market. That is KM model can be used for every stage of the engineering works such us design, manufacture, maintenance and repair.

FIG. 1: KM MODEL

III. APPLICATION OF THE KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ON MACHINING SYSTEM

By manufacturing system we understand all the technological systems that are used to produce a specific product.

Each of these technological systems is composed of machine-tool, tools, devices, parts, operator and carries out one of the operations of the technological process of making that product.

The machining system performance depends on how it is run. In more specialized papers [1] reference is made to the relationships between the parameters of the processing regimes and the technical performance of the machining system (purely technical aspects), while in others, equally numerous [4], [5] references are made to the relationship between the product made by the machining system and the market (economic relations).

In the literature no attempt to approach the whole machining system – market assembly is reported; therefore, there are significant resources to improve performance which are not used because the technical and economic aspects are dealt with separately.

Also, it is not known an algorithm for the management of the machining system – market assembly, but only algorithms for the technical control of the technological systems [5] and tools of economic management of the relationship between the technological system as a whole and the market [6].

Nowadays, the machining systems are controlled by means of numerically programmed machine tools which are part of the system [7]. The control is exclusively technical because there is no economic variable, although this is actually the ultimate goal of any processing process.

The dynamic changes and the overall progress of society are reflected at company level by many orders in number, small in volume, very diverse, obtained through frequent auctions with short- term response, which leaves no time for a relevant analysis of said orders.

As a result, a long-term management is no longer possible. A sort of fluctuating (just like the market) on-line, fast responsive, prompt and rapid, however, ephemeral management is called for [4]. For these goals we propose knowledge management model of machining system.

The architecture of KM model of machining system is presented in Fig. 2. The system showed in Fig. 2 consists of KM model, CNC Machining System, Marketing Knowledge.

FIG. 2. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ARCHITECTURE OF THE MACHINING SYSTEM

KM model contains very important features of the system.

KM model consists of knowledge bank, compare, modeling and control units. The knowledge bank is formed according to the characteristics of the system.

It is very important that information which concerns with subject, correct, update, concordant must be converted knowledge and they must be stored in this unit. It is necessary that this unit becomes a flexible structure because it can be updated depending on the market dynamics and technical characteristics of the new manufacturing products.

The information coming from the Marketing Knowledge-unit are diagnosed by the comparison unit. Also the comparison unit has information-receive ability from knowledge bank. The essential function of the comparison unit is to compare the information and knowledge with each other. The output information from the comparison units is a new knowledge. This new knowledge has been sent to modeling unit.

Not only does the modeling unit receive information from the comparison unit, it also interacts with the knowledge bank. The output of the modeling unit is the model which is analyzed in control unit. This unit sends the manufacturing instruction for to the CNC Machining System. Through on-line learning, the output information from CNC Machining System unit becomes the new knowledge and has been sent to knowledge bank.

On the other hand, after assessing competitiveness, the management system should enable to develop competitive offer for the tenders. To achieve these two objectives, the competitive control uses the reinforcement learning to get to know the market and the non supervised on-line learning technique to get to know the machining system.

IV. STUDY CASE

Let us assume that in market there are more offers quotations for a certain product. Using reinforcement learning, the information from market becomes marketing knowledge and they are compared with the ones from knowledge bank.

After the comparison, knowledge unit send the technical-economic parameters to the modeling unit. Also, modeling unit interacts with the knowledge bank to achieve the machining model.

On basis of generated model, simulations are made and analyzed in control unit. This unit sends to the CNC machining system the manufacturing instructions that satisfy the customer demands in the competitive conditions of the enterprise.

For example, from the simulations (Fig. 3.a) it can see that the minimum cost is obtained for the cutting speed $v'_{op}=84\text{m/min}$. The control unit sends to the CNC machining system the manufacturing parameters: cutting speed v'_{op} , feed rate s , depth of cut t .

Also, corresponding to this cutting speed, it can be read the necessary time τ for 1 cm^2 surface area machining (Fig. 3.b), the profit rate r (Fig. 3.c) and the environmental impact I (Fig. 3.d). On basis of these simulations the manager can decide if the order is accepted or rejected.

FIG. 3. SIMULATIONS FOR A TURNING PROCESS AND SYSTEM: a) STRUCTURE OF THE COST c ; b) TIME τ ; c) PROFIT RATE r ; d) ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT I

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper the architecture of the knowledge management of the machining system was achieved.

Using and comparing marketing knowledge with stored and updated ones the machining model is carried out, analyzed and on its basis are generated instructions regarding the progress of the machining process in order to obtain maximum competitiveness.

By modeling and simulations, the manager can decide if the order is accepted and control the machining system to satisfy the customer demands.

To achieve these objectives, the competitive control uses the reinforcement learning to get to know the market and the unsupervised on-line learning technique to get to know the machining system.

Note that we propose to give managers a knowledge management model, so that they can interact with the economic environment (market).

This knowledge management model represents a technical-economic model that can be used for competitive control of the manufacturing process without requesting experiments and based on the extraction of the knowledge from the previous experience.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cios K., Pedrycz W., Siniarski R., Kurgan L., „Data Mining- A knowledge Discovery Approach”, Springer, 2007.
- [2] Christoph H. L., Chick S. and Huchzermeier A., „Can European Manufacturing Companies Compete?: Industrial Competitiveness Employment and Growth in Europe“, European Management Journal, Volume 25, Issue 4, August, 2007, pp.251-265.
- [3] H'nida F., Martin P., Vernadat F., „Cost estimation in mechanical production, The Cost Entity approach applied to integrated product engineering”, International Journal of Production Economics, 103, 2006, pp.17-35.
- [4] Hoda A. ElMaraghy, „Flexible and reconfigurable manufacturing systems paradigms“, Springer Science+Business Media, LLC, 2006, pp.261-276.
- [5] Karayel D., Ozkan S., Keles R., „General framework for distributed knowledge management in mechatronic systems“, Journal of intelligent manufacturing, 2004, pp.511-515.
- [6] Lerch F.J., Harter D.E., „Cognitive support for real-time dynamic decision making”, Information System Research, 12(1), 2001, pp.63-82.
- [7] Toly C., „Evaluating the mid-term competitiveness of a product in a semiconductor fabrication factory with a systematic procedure“, Computers & Industrial Engineering, Volume 53, Issue 3, October, 2007, pp.499-513.